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Corporate Characteristics and Dividend Policy of Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of firm characteristics on the dividend policy of the consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to examine the effect of. Board Size, Board Independence, Chief Executive Officer Duality, Ownership concentration, Institutional Ownership, and Managerial Ownership on on dividend payout ratio. The study covered a sample of nine consumer goods firms within an eight-year time frame from 2013 to 2020. The panel regression model was employed and Hausman test used to select between Fixed and Random effects for result interpretation. The findings showed that corporate governance has significant effect, driven by board independence, institutional ownership and Chief Executive Officer Duality on the dividend policy of consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study concluded that corporate characteristics are determinants of dividend policies of quoted firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that investors with risk averse attitude needing quick return on investment should consider larger firms that have higher propensity to pay dividend.

Keywords: Corporate Characteristics, Dividend Policy, Consumer Goods Firms, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Businesses around the world have their primary goals as the maximisation of returns to the owners of the business. Amongst the returns to corporate businesses are dividend payments and capital gains (appreciation). The capital appreciation comes from the increasing market value of quoted stock due to market factors like share demands, information, and firm value. The dividend payment comes in form of cash, bonus issue or repurchasing shares (Arnold, 2009; Alaeto, 2020). Among these variations of dividend payments, a cash dividend is the most common means of profit sharing with the advantage of meeting the liquidity needs of investors and signalling the current and future prospects of a firm to shareholders (Pandey, 2005). However, cash dividends may reduce the amount of funds retained by a company to finance its future growth and investments; this may force a company to have more external borrowing which may lead to more regulatory scrutiny and higher costs of financing (Ozo, 2014).

In corporate businesses where the owners are different from the management, the management are motivated to formulate policies that will maximize shareholders' wealth. The policies and decisions will include (amongst others) investment, financing and dividend policy decisions. Dividend policy is the aspect of financial management function that fine-tunes the proportion of firm's profit that should be distributed to the shareholders and the proportion to be retained for additional investment. Whichever options the management adopts, whether or not to pay and what proportion to distribute from earnings constitute a topical issue in finance and has created a concept described as the dividend payment puzzle.

This explains why Black (1976) noted that “the harder we look at the dividend picture, the more it seems like puzzle, with pieces that do not fit together”.

In Nigeria, the dividend payment puzzle was moderated by some enabling laws that tend to regulate the payment of dividends by shareholders in Nigeria. These regulations place restrictions to the dividend payout not to exceed certain percentage. These restrictions may include government policy on the proportion of earnings to be distributed, while the second restriction may be the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) which governs the operation of registered companies in Nigeria. The CAMA stipulates in section 379(2), that the annual general meeting has the power to reduce the amount of proposed dividend. One of the reasons behind the dividend decision policy of the Nigerian government is to ensure that funds are available for continuous investment in assets, so that the companies will continue to operate on the growing concern principle (Sanyaolu, Onifade & Ajulo, 2017). These restrictions did not however, determine the bench marks for dividend payment. As Black (1976) pointed out, the factors that determine dividend payment is replete and diverse as there are characteristics. Further studies has merely contributed to the multiple paradoxes of corporate dividend policy, thereby adding more pieces to an enlarged puzzle rather than finding the final matching piece that would provide a more precise and complete understanding of the determinants of dividend policy.

Among the theories that have arisen from inception are the Modigliani and Miller’s (1961) dividend irrelevant theory, the Gordon’s (1962) bird in hand theory, Litzenberger and Ramaswamy’s (1979) tax preference theory, the Lintner’s (1956) information content and signalling theory, the Bhattacharya’s (1979) clientele effect theory, the Jensen and Meckling’s (1976) agency cost and free cash flow theory and the recent catering theory (Baker & Wurgler, 2004).

Modigliani and Miller (1961) show that in perfect capital market with no information asymmetry and predetermined investment decision, the value of the firms is independent of the financing decisions. Hence, a firm’s financing decision including dividends, has no effect on the value of the firm, or the distribution of wealth between classes of security holders. However, imperfect situation abound in real life such that dividend can influence shareholders wealth by providing information to investors or through wealth redistribution among claimants. It can be argued that dividends provide information about the firm’s future cash flow and as such decision bothering on dividend can effect a change on a firm’s value (Iheduru & Okoro, 2018).

These theories have been empirically tested both in the developed and developing economies. The recent issue is that corporate dividend policies vary across countries and are influenced by institutional factors associated with corporate governance and some characteristics of the firms including profitability, capital structure liquidity and even size (Sanyaolu, Onifade & Ajulo, 2017; Aldini, Santoso & Putra, 2018; Afensimi & Izedomni, 2019; Zulfikar, Nofianti, Dwi Astuti, Meutia & Ramadan, 2020; Hettiarachchi & Samarakoon, 2020). A plethora of empirical evidences examined has shown conflicting findings as regards the determinant of dividend policy. The desire to address these shortcomings prompted us to embark on this study

Statement of the Problem

Dividend payment strategy has remained a problem such that a plethora of studies had been done for many decades, but there has not been universally accepted explanation on how firms can develop and manage dividend behaviour across economies and business sectors. The paucity of available theories to explain how dividend policy can be determined and distributed to satisfy shareholder’s investment objective has remained a mirage in corporate literature. This is even a serious issue for the consumer goods sector Nigeria with highly competitive and dynamic market where investors would crave for strategies to optimize their returns.

Empirical evidences on corporate governance and decision policy nexus for Nigerian firms have remained conflicting and at best mixed for decades with more diverse opinion in the areas of liquidity, and financial leverage. Gaps abound in empirical evidences on effects of corporate governance, profitability, capital structure, liquidity and even firm size on dividend policy in the consumer goods firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. For instance, specific attention has been given to holistic sector, (Afensimi & Izedomni, 2019), non-financial firms (Odeleye, 2017, and Nwidobie, 2020), and the banking industry

(Kurawa & Ishaku, 2014) in Nigeria, yet none has singled out the consumer goods sector for consideration of corporate governance. More so, most studies on profitability- dividend nexus in Nigeria have employed return on asset, return on equity or earnings per share or a combination of them (Adepoju, Ogunyemi & Onafadeji, 2019; Sanyaolu, *et al* 2017). Nonetheless, return on capital employed is a more comprehensive measure of management efficiency than return on asset; and not any study is known to have considered the profit margin paradigm that weigh returns against sales volume. Moreover, firm size has no known indebt extant literature to explain effect of corporate governance on dividend policy. More to this is that extant studies on liquidity as determinant of dividend only considered the current ratio in exclusion of the effect of cash flows. As dividend has been one of the drivers of market reactions, a study to explain how firm characteristics, such as corporate governance, profitability, size, liquidity and capital structure, influence it will give limelight to investment analysis for investment windows in the Nigerian stock market.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Dividend

The dividend is the reward for equity capital. To investors in the stock of a firm entitles investors the ownership rights to guarantee them a share from the profit or loss of the firm. Dividend is the entitlement to the proportion of the profit declared for distribution to the shareholders. We describe it as an entitlement because it is the reward for the risk undertaken and the gain for investment into ownership right of a firm. In the words of Sanyaolu, Onifade

and Ajulo (2017), "Dividend is the payment by a company to its shareholders out of its distributable profit as a reward for investments". In other words, payment from a distributable profit means that it is payable from the revenue remaining as profits after all other stakeholders have been settled. The risk burden on the shareholder arises from being the last receiver of reward from the business revenue.

For an investor, the dividend is just one of the gains of investment. They can wait for capital appreciation that can be due to increase in the value (net worth) of the firm or from the share of the profit distributable which we called a dividend. A firm is not obliged to pay out the profit of the business at the end of the financial year. The firm may reinvest and expect increased returns that will improve future rewards to shareholders. Any of the options of either to pay or not and what proportion to distribute from firm profit connotes dividend policy.

A firm put forward some yardsticks, and strategies to determine and suggest when and how firm profitability should be administered for the optimal gains to the owners of the business and benefit of other stakeholders in the system. This defines the concept of dividend policy.

Dividend Policy

Dividend Policy defines the "amount of dividend payments and the amounts of retained earnings for reinvesting in new projects" (Iheduru & Okoro, 2018). The policy fashioned out the suitable proportion for dividing the profit after taxation into the immediate payments to shareholders and reinvestment in new business opportunities. The policy covers such issues bothering on proposing the payout, method of payment and the aggregate retention of earnings policy that management follows in determining the size and pattern of cash distributions to shareholders over time (Iheduru & Okoro, 2018).

A dividend policy is not a plan cast in stone. It is only a set of guidelines employed by a firm to decide how much of its earnings it will pay out to shareholders (Morakinyo, David, Adeleke & Omojola, 2018).

This guideline only aims to give flexibility to investors on how to manage and utilise returns on their investment. According to Morakinyo, David, Adeleke and Omojola (2018), "...investors are not concerned with a company's dividend policy since they can sell a portion of their portfolio of equities if they want cash".

The primary interest of the investors in dividend policy is that it serves to maximise the net worth of the shareholders. The optimal dividend policy of a firm depends on investor's desire for capital gains as opposed to income, their willingness to forgo dividends now for future returns, and their perception of the risk associated with postponement of returns, therefore management should not retain income unless they

can reinvest those earnings at higher rates of return than shareholders can earn themselves (Brigham & Houston 2009). This is why Kurawa and Ishaku (2014) were of the opinion that dividend and retained earnings are an opposite of each other, yet they still go hand in hand since it's not possible to formulate one without having an effect on the other, therefore, a company must strike a balance between the two by finding a dividend payout ratio that will provide sufficient equity to support the capital budget without having to sell new common stock or take the capital structure ratios outside the optimal range.

The essence of dividend policy is to guide the management to plan on the size, distribution channel and retention of capital. This is what Iheduru and Okoro (2018) identified as three-pronged aspects of dividend policies size, distribution channel or the form of resources with which to pay rewards and then the amount to apportion for new ventures. Nonetheless, most literature has employed the size of the payment to define and investigate dividend policy issues across economies.

Consumer Goods Firms in Nigerian Stock Exchange

Consumer goods is one of the eleven sectors under which the quoted firms are classified by the Nigeria Stock Exchange. The market is the group for the firms in the category of "stocks and companies that relate to items purchased by individuals and households rather than by manufacturers and industries" (Scott, 2020). These groups of companies are in the business of making and selling products that serve the wants of the direct consumer for their use and enjoyment. According to Scott (2020), the consumer goods sector is involved with food production, packaged goods, clothing, beverages, automobiles, and electronics, which are directly used by the buyers in the household and for personal consumption.

The consumer goods sector in Nigeria is rated as a big market but the majority of its market share is dominated by the low-income groups. The demographic features of Nigeria are attractive to the consumer industry to thrive. The large population size of the country makes it a destination of a huge market for consumer-facing companies and retailers. According to World Bank data, Nigeria, South Africa and Egypt - contributes above 50.0% of Africa's total consumer spending.

Firm Characteristics

Firm characteristics portend the basic features of a company which can be described and evaluated. These characteristics are corporate governance, profitability, capital structure, liquidity and size. These characteristics have been explained in literature to relate to and determine the dividend policy of quoted firms. In this context, dividend policy is conceptualised to depend on selected firm characteristics (corporate governance, profitability, capital structure, liquidity and size).

The management of a business is governed by a set of rules. Corporate governance is a term used to describe how business organisations were governed (Lazarides, Drimpetas & Dimitrios, 2009). Since the management is different from the ownership, the rules of corporate governance try to protect shareholders and the interest of other stakeholders by ensuring transparency and enforcing accountability within the business organisation. Corporate governance is the system by which companies are directed and controlled. Boards of directors are responsible for the governance of their companies. The shareholders' role in governance is to appoint the directors and the auditors and to satisfy themselves that an appropriate governance structure is in place.

The tenets of corporate governance enhance a healthy professional relationship among the stakeholders which include board directors, managers, employees, customers, regulators and most notably, shareholders. The core pillars on which successful corporate governance is hinged are accountability, fairness, transparency, assurance, leadership and stakeholder management (Gitau, 2015). The principle of accountability in corporate governance pertains to the embracing ownership of strategy and tasks required to attain organisational goals.

Organisations are expected to analyse and assess its reward and risk contents in a clear context of a predetermined value proposition. The idea of fairness portends "treating all stakeholders s including minorities, reasonably, equitably and provide effective redress for violations" (Gitau, 2015). This requires an effective communication mechanism that can ensure objective and appropriate safety of resources and people assets as well as correcting of wrongs. The pillar of transparency "means having nothing to hide" that allows its processes and transactions observable to outsiders. It also makes necessary disclosures and informs everyone affected about its decisions. Transparency is a critical component of corporate

governance that ensures that all the actions of the organisation can be monitored and assessed by all stakeholders at any given time. This ensures that the processes and transactions of the organisation are verifiable. Transparency enhances sound investment decision since all material information is available to outsiders.

A company that has sound corporate governance guidelines that facilitates the independence of the non-directors. Independent assurance is the verification by a third party (not directly responsible for quality assurance and acceptance of the product/deliverable and/or the reliability of test results obtained from quality control and acceptance testing). This independent assurance ensures that (1) the representation or acceptance test results are accurate and provide a fair and equitable basis for construction acceptance and (2) quality control testing is accurate and thus will properly indicate process quality. Nonetheless, leadership is another essential pillar of corporate governance. Leadership ensure that the origination's agenda is within the values and principles that frame the way business should be done (Roman, 2020).

The two tenets of corporate governance structure are the board of the organisation and the ownership structure. Juhmani (2020) described the board and ownership structure as corporate governance mechanisms.

Theoretical Framework

Dividend Irrelevance Theory (Modigliani and Miller (MM))

Modigliani and Miller (1961) in their seminal contribution to research on Dividend policy argued that the value of the firm is independent of its dividend policy. MM argued that the value of a firm depends only on the income produced by firm assets and not on how this income is split between dividends and retained earnings. MM further noted that any shareholder can in theory construct its own dividend policy, e.g. if a firm does not pay dividends, a shareholder who wants 10% dividends can create it by selling 10% of his stock. They argued that if investors could buy and sell shares and thus create their own dividends without incurring costs, then the firm's dividend policy would truly be irrelevant.

MM further supported their argument by saying that, if a firm does not have sufficient cash to pay dividends and therefore issues new shares to finance the payment of dividends then, the shareholders get the new shares in the form of dividends but suffer an equal amount of capital loss since the value of their claim on assets reduces. Thus the wealth of the shareholders does not change. The new shareholders part with their cash in exchange for new shares and the existing shareholders transfer part of their claim to the new shareholders in exchange for cash. Thus there is no net gain or loss and the value of the firm will remain un- altered after the transaction. MM based their argument on the assumption that there is no corporate taxes, no transaction cost associated with the flotation of new shares, capital markets are efficient, and there is no uncertainty, all investors make decisions using the same discount rate.

Bird in the Hand Theory

The proponent of this theory Lintner (1962) and Gordon (1962) argued that capital will decrease as the dividend pay-out is increased because investors are less certain of receiving the capital gains that are supposed to be realized from the retention of earnings than receiving the dividends. They argued in effect that investors value a shilling of expected dividends more highly than a shilling of expected capital gains because the dividend yield component is less risky than the growth component in the total expected return equation. The theory implies that investors are risk averse and attaches less risk to the current dividend than to future dividend or capital gain. Current dividend payment (bird in hand) reduces investors' uncertainty and hence results in higher values of the firms' stocks. Given that investors prefer less uncertainty, they would prefer dividends to capital gains. Therefore a company paying high dividends will attract more investors, increase the demand for its shares and thus the increase value of the firm. Thus the higher the dividend, the higher the value of the firm and vice versa.

Empirical Review

Afensimi and Izedomni (2019) carried out a study that examined whether ownership structure of quoted Nigerian firms has relationship with their dividend policy. The study desegregated ownership structure into managerial ownership, institutional ownership and foreign ownership as the independent variables

and controlled for firm size and profitability. Dividend policy being the dependent variable was captured with dividend payout ratio. The sample of 70 firms were selected and data covering eight (8) years from 2009 to 2016 were collected. The study regressed the model using pooled, fixed effect, random and GMM effect and the Hausman test supported fixed effect model for result interpretation. The baseline results showed that foreign ownership and institutional ownership has significant positive effects on dividend payment while managerial ownership though positive but did not influence dividend. However, it was found that the effect of ownership structure on dividend payment is significantly moderated by profitability. The study thus recommended the adoption of diverse ownership structure has corporate governance model in Nigeria.

Odeleye (2017) did a study that examined the moderating effect of sectorial disaggregation of corporate governance on the dividend payment in Nigeria. Corporate governance was represented by number of independent directors, institutional investors, board size and managerial shareholding while dividend per share captured the dividend policy in Nigeria. A sample of 97 non-financial listed companies in Nigeria between 1995 and 2012 were selected for the study. All the sectors in Nigeria were captured into agriculture, automobile, building, brewery, chemical/paints, conglomerates, construction, food and beverages, healthcare, industrial/domestic products, petroleum and printing/publishing sub-sectors. The analysis was performed at both aggregate and sectorial level using the system generalised method of moment estimation technique to accommodate firm level characteristics and manage autocorrelation bias. The results revealed that corporate governance and dividend payment have positive association. This explains that previous dividend, number of independent directors, institutional investors, profits after tax and gross earnings are drivers of corporate decisions and consequently dividend pay-outs in Nigeria. The study posits that mode of operations (proxied by sector classification) are important in explaining the relationship between corporate governance practices and dividend pay-outs in Nigeria. The study therefore suggested that the number of independent directors on the boards of corporate firms and the proportion of institutional shareholding should be increased to improve monitoring.

Oskar and Talavera (2008) examined the relationship between corporate governance practices and dividend payouts in Poland. The study employed the Transparency Disclosure Index (TDI) as main variable and Board structure and procedures, Disclosure and Shareholders as sub-variables of corporate governance. A sample of 110 non-financial companies listed on the Warsaw Stock Exchange between 1998 and 2004 were selected and analysed using the t-test and Wilcoxon ranked test. The results showed that TDI and its three sub-indices significantly positively influenced cash dividend in Poland. The results suggests that corporate governance that protected shareholders in Poland enhanced their powers to extract dividends from firms. On the basis of the agency theory, the study suggested that firms with strong corporate governance standards can easily mitigate agency conflicts from the use of free cash flow for dividends instead of for further investments with a negative net present value.

Kurawa and Ishaku (2014) examined the effect of corporate governance on dividend policy of five selected commercial banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2003 and 2012. Data was collected from the Annual reports and accounts of the sampled banks. A panel data methodology (Random-effect GLS regression technique) was employed for the analysis of data. The results reveal that management equity holding has significant effect on dividend payout ratio, Board size and CEO duality has insignificant effect, while board independence exhibit negative but insignificant effect. It is recommended that since the fundamental purpose of any company is the creation and delivery of long-term sustainable value in a manner consistent with their obligations as a responsible corporate citizen, then the Bank should therefore views corporate governance not as an end in itself but a vital facilitator to the creation of long- term value for all stakeholders. And to enhance the level of influence of Corporate Governance on Dividend Payout Ratio to higher level in the Nigerian Banking Industry, Management equity holding should be increased as this will make the management to protect not only their interest but the interest of all stakeholders.

Zulfikar, Nofianti, Dwi Astuti, Meutia and Ramadan (2020) carried out a study to examine the role of ownership's concentration as a moderator of the relationship between dividend policy effects and firm value in Indonesia. Price to Book Value (PBV) was used as proxy for firm value and Dividend Payout

Ratio (DPR) as the dependent variables was moderated with concentration of ownership, size and leverage. A sample of 23 firms generated for a period of five years spanning 2014 and 2018 were analysed using the Moderate Regression Analysis (MRA). The results showed that dividend policy had a positive effect on firm value. As well, firms whose ownership had been owned by families would affect management policies, such as dividend policy. The study implies that business ethics in Indonesia had been weak and thus there is need to strengthen corporate governance in the economy.

Using a time frame covering 2006 to 2014, Ali, Hanming and Ullah (2018) examined the effects of ownership and board structure on dividend smoothing in Pakistani listed banks. The study employed board size, board independence, audit size, CEO-duality, management, foreign and majority ownership as proxies for corporate governance while Speed of Adjustment (SOA) to dividend payment was used as proxy for dividend smoothing. The sample of 19 banks listed on the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) within a period of 9 years (2006 to 2014) was regressed using random Tobit technique. The principal component analysis (PCA) was employed to develop a corporate governance index. The findings revealed that banks with concentrated and foreign ownership, small size audit committee and less independent boards, show higher levels of dividend smoothing. However, banks have joint positions CEO and chairperson, showed lesser dividend smoothing. The study posits that increased dividends are sound monitoring mechanism for shareholders within a weak corporate governance environment.

Nwidobie (2013) employed a multiple regression model to identify the determinants of dividend policy in quoted firms in Nigeria. 14 factors were incorporated as independent variables as profitability of the firm, cost of paying dividend, stability of earnings, prospects of raising capital from the capital market, shareholders characteristics, shareholders' needs and requests, availability of investment opportunities, growth prospects of the firm, restriction by lenders, market value of the firm, firm policy, rate of inflation, industry declaration rate, industry declaration rate. Naira dividend paid was the dependent variable. The structured questionnaires was administered on 21 (of the 214) quoted firms on the Nigerian stock exchange on dividend policy. The results revealed that complaints of shareholders does not have significant effect on naira dividend paid by the firms. However, it was found that there is an inverse relationship between the needs and desires of shareholders and the naira dividend paid by the firms. The study recommended that institution of good corporate governance structure should be the finest solution to agency problems in quoted firms that would create better decision structure for dividend in Nigerian firms.

Yousaf, Ali, and Hassan (2019) examined the impact of family control on the dividend policy of firms in Pakistan. Data were gathered from 54 family firms and 49 non-family firms for a period covering 2009 to 2016. The study aimed to also investigate the extent to which of family control moderates the impact of firm-specific factors on the dividend policy. The GMM model for panel data estimation is used. The mean difference univariate analysis shows that family firms differ from nonfamily firms based on financial characteristics. The multivariate analysis shows that family firms pay lower dividends than nonfamily firms. On the overall, the study posited that family control, size, and tangibility are the major determinants of the dividend policy in Pakistan.

Awwad and Hamdan (2018) carried out a study to identify the corporate governance variables in the Gulf financial markets, energy sectors and to determine its effects on dividend policy. A sample of 8 energy firms covering a period of 10 years from 2008 to 2017 from six Gulf financial markets: Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates. The corporate governance was measured using managerial ownership, size of board of directors, independence of board of directors, Duality of CEO with size, leverage and growth as moderating variables, whereas payout ratio is the dependent variable. The OLS and logistic regressions showed that firms with good governance seek to distribute the profits among shareholders to reduce the conflict of interests and reduce the agency costs. Thus corporate governance has positive and significant effect on dividend policy.

Al-Kahmisi and Hassan (2018) examined the effect of corporate governance on dividend payout policies in Malaysian banks. The study correlated board size, board independence, and CEO duality with dividend yield. A sample of six banks from public listed companies within a period of five years from 2011 to 2015 were used. The correlation and ANOVA results showed that CEO duality and board independence

has negative relationship to the company dividend policy. Further analysis showed that board size has no effect on dividend policy. The core recommendation is that the corporate governance level in Malaysia should be improved.

Kajola, Olabisi, Soyemi, and Olayiwola, (2019) examined the effect of proportional representation of female as directors in corporate boards on the dividend policy amongst 19 listed consumer goods and industrial companies in Nigeria covering 7 years from 2010 to 2016. Dividend pay share served as the dependent variable while Proportion of female directors to total board membership and Absolute number of female directors on board were the independent variables controlled by firm size, board size and profitability. The results from Random Effects Generalised Least Squares (REGLS) model revealed that a positive and significant association between the number of women in corporate boardrooms and dividend policy.

Nwidobie (2020) carried a study to investigate the effect of board diversity on the dividend per share of listed nonfinancial firms in Nigeria in both the short and long-terms. Board diversity was disaggregated into proportion of female, male and minority members of the boards of directors. A sample of nine firms for a period of 2010 to 2018 were analysed using multivariate log-linear regression model. The results indicated that increasing the proportion males on the board has positive effect on dividend per share while increasing the proportion of females and minority shareholders on the boards had negative effects on dividend per share both in the short and long-runs. The study posits that shareholders interested in higher dividend per share should appoint more males, and less females and minorities to the board.

Juhmani (2020) evaluated the effect of corporate governance using board characteristics and ownership structure on dividend payout decision of firms Bahrain within 2014 and 2016. The dependent variable was captured as the dividend payout ratio while the independent variables were board independence, board size, frequency of board meetings, blockholder ownership, institutional ownership and managerial ownership. Results from multiple OLS regression that board independence has a significant negative association with the dividend payout decision, and board size has a significant positive association with the dividend payout decision. Other variables including the frequency of board meetings and ownership structure (blockholder ownership, institutional ownership, managerial ownership) did not have significant effect on the dividend payout decisions.

La Ode (2018) investigated the effect of corporate governance on dividend payout ratio amongst publicly listed firms in Indonesia between 2013 and 2016. The specific variables of the study are ownership structure and corporate governance mechanisms on dividend payout ratio using panel data regression model. The findings of the study indicate that board independence, board size, institutional ownership, size and earnings before interest and tax are positive; whereas the CEO duality, managerial ownership, ownership concentration and leverage are in negative relation with dividend payout ratio.

Gap in Reviewed Literature

A study on corporate governance and dividend policy nexus has been done in Nigeria aggregated all sectors in Nigeria (Afensimi & Izedomni, 2019), non-financial firms (Odeleye, 2017, and Nwidobie, 2020), and the banking industry (Kurawa & Ishaku, 2014). The sole study that targeted the consumer goods firms did so in combination with the sister industrial goods sector (Kajola, *at el*, 2019). Nonetheless, the study did not embrace all facets of the corporate governance paradigm as it dealt with on the factors of female involvement of board management like the ratio of female in directorship position, bad the absolute number of female directors. Thus, studies that would be all embracing in examining the corporate governance variables that determine dividend policy would incorporate other board composition variables as well as ownership structure issues. This is lacking in extant literature in Nigeria. Firm profitability is the driving force for dividend policies. However, most studies of the firm profitability and dividend policy nexus in Nigeria used either the return on asset (Adepoju, *et al* 2019) or other variant of profitability indicator (EPS and ROE) (Sanyaolu, *et al* 2017). Nonetheless, return on capital employed is a more comprehensive measure of management efficiency than return on asset. A study that would incorporate all the essential profitability indicators in one model might make a sound model for profitability and dividend policy nexus in Nigeria.

The study revealed a dearth of distinct empirical studies those targets to find out the effects of firm size on dividend policy. No empirical study has incorporated all the measures of firm size covering asset, sales and stock market dimensions to size determination. More so, the study on liquidity have either employed the current ratio (current asset divided by current liability) or a variant of firms forms of stock. The consumer goods sector being a well-developed sector in Nigeria, yet highly competitive and thriving, it is expected that investors interested in dividend payment would crave for strategies to enhance dividend payment of prospective firms.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The *ex-post-facto* research design adopted for this study. The population of the study consist of all the 20 consumer goods firms quoted on the Nigeria Stock Exchange as at April, 2021. 17 of these firms formed the sample for the study. This is about 85% of the target population.

Table 1: List of consumer goods firms quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at April, 2021.

SN	Name of Company	Acronym
1	Cadbury Nigeria Plc.	CADBURY
2	Champion Brew. Plc.	CHAMPION
3	Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc	DANGSUGAR
4	DN Tyre & Rubber Plc	DUNLOP
5	Flour Mills Nig. Plc.	FLOUR
6	Golden Guinea Brew. Plc.	GOLDBREW
7	Guinness Nig Plc	GUINNESS
8	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc	HONYFLOUR
9	International Breweries Plc.	INTBREW
10	McNichols Plc	MCNICHOLS
11	Multi-Trex Integrated Foods Plc	MULTITREX
12	Northern Nig. Flour Mills Plc.	NNFM
13	Nascon Allied Industries Plc	NASCON
14	Nestle Nigeria Plc	NESTLE
15	Nigerian Breweries Plc.	NB
16	Nigerian Enamelware Plc.	ENAMELWARE
17	P Z Cussons Nigeria Plc.	PZ
18	Unilever Nigeria Plc.	UNILEVER
19	Union Dicon Salt Plc.	UNIONDICON
20	Vitafoam Nigeria Plc.	VITAFOAM

Sources: Nigerian Stock Exchange (2021). <http://www.nse.com.ng/issuers/listed-securities/listed-companies>

Model of Corporate Governance and Dividend Policy Nexus

The model for objective one aims to regress corporate governance variables on dividend policy. The work of La Ode (2018) that was done in Indonesia was adapted. His model is state thus:

$$DPR = f(OC, IO, MO, BS, BI, CEOD)$$

Where:

DPR = Dividend payout ratio

BI = Board independence

BS = Board Size

IO = Institutional ownership

CEOD = Chief Executive Officer Duality

MO = Managerial Ownership

OC = Ownership concentration

This model showed the most comprehensive inclusion of all corporate governance variables to examine its effect on dividend policy. Unlike other studies reviewed in Nigeria, none had incorporated sizeable ownership and board composition variables in one model as the above. However, the present model imported a control for firm size to explain that larger firms may differ from smaller ones in the area of board size and independence, CEO duality and even institutional involvement. Thus the model can be rewritten as econometric equation as follows:

$$DPR_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 BI_{it} + \beta_2 BS_{it} + \beta_3 IO_{it} + \beta_4 CEOD_{it} + \beta_5 MO_{it} + \beta_6 OC + \beta_7 FS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

FS = firm size measured by the natural log of total asset

t is the time period spanning 2011 to 2020, and i is the cross section of firms.

β_{1-7} are the coefficient of regression for the seven corporate governance variables

μ is the error term

Panel regression model are developed for the study. The Fixed Effect Model and Random Effect Model will be used for the analysis. The pre-estimation analysis will include descriptive statistics covering mean, and standard deviation of the variables; and the Hausman test that will determine the most suitable tool of analysis. The post estimation analysis will be the diagnostic test that will cover the multicollinearity, Heteroskedasticity, and normal distribution test.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Analysis of the Descriptive Statistics of the Dividend Policy and Corporate Governance Variables

	DPR	BI	BS	IO	CEOD	MO	OC	FS
Mean	1.21	0.47	10.03	0.56	0.67	0.44	0.53	17.98
Std. Dev.	4.84	0.19	1.60	0.12	0.47	0.21	0.18	1.07
Jarque-Bera	3471.35	2.47	4.02	7.29	12.75	1.84	10.11	2.32
Probability	0.00	0.29	0.13	0.03	0.00	0.40	0.01	0.31
Observations	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72

The descriptive on Table 3 revealed the nature and normality of corporate governance data. The mean value for dividend payout ratio (DPR) being the dependent variable is 1.21. The corresponding mean value is 4.84. There is a very wide variation between the average DPR and the standard deviation. This suggests that the selected firm have dissimilarity in dividend policies. There is tendency for lack of normal distribution in the DPR series.

The corporate governance variables are the BI, BS, IO, CEOD, MO, and OC. The mean values for these data are 0.47, 10, 03, 0,56, 0.67, 0.44 and 0.53, respectively. These Mean tends to larger than the respective standard deviation. This suggests very close variation and hence propensity for normal distribution in the series. The control variable being the Firm Size (FS) has a mean of 17.98 and standard deviation of 1.07. Similarly, it shows possibility of presence of normal distribution. The test for normality from Jacque Bera statistics showed p.values for DPR, IO, CEOD, and OC as 0.00, 0.03, 0.00 and 0.01, which are less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence we reject the null hypothesis and posit that they lack normal distribution. The Jacque Bera p.values for BI, BS, MO and FS are 0.29, 0.13, 0.40 and 0.31 which are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence we cannot reject the null hypothesis and posit that they have normal distribution.

Effect of Corporate Governance on Dividend Policy

Table 3: Regression result of the relationship between corporate governance and dividend policy

Dependent Variable: DPR

Sample: 2013 2020

Periods included: 8

Cross-sections included: 9

Total panel (balanced) observations: 72

Independent Variables	Fixed Effect Model			Random Effect Model *Preferred		
	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
BI	4.2032	0.8382	0.4054	3.7458	4.7499	0.0060
BS	0.3838	0.9376	0.3524	0.3319	0.8054	0.4235
IO	-0.4644	-5.0425	0.0062	-1.6223	-8.1521	0.0096
CEOD	-3.7252	-11.4392	0.0055	-3.9105	-2.4963	0.0395
MO	2.8301	0.3974	0.6925	3.2310	0.4509	0.6536
OC	-3.6810	-0.7185	0.4754	-2.6691	-0.5178	0.6064
FS	-0.6624	-0.8131	0.4195	-0.4506	-0.5497	0.5845
C	10.7330	0.5177	0.6066	7.7126	0.3713	0.7116
R-Squared	0.2103			0.3168		
F-statistic (Prob)	15.0845 (0.0005)			6.2100 (0.0102)		
Durbin Watson (DW)	2.0965			2.2790		
Hausman test	4.4334 (0.6182)					

Source: Extract from Eviews Results

The analysis for the interpretation of objective one is shown on Table 10. The Table showed least square regression results based on Fixed Effect and Random Effect. The Hausman test was employed to determine the most suitable tool of analysis between the fixed and random effect models. The result of the Hausman statistics is 4.4334 with 0.6182 probability value. Since the p.value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the study did not reject the null hypothesis that the random effect model is preferred. Hence, the study adopted to random effect model to interpret the effect of corporate governance on dividend policy amongst consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The result indicates that both cross-section and period effect influence the outcome of the analysis.

From the results, the R-square is 0.3168 which indicates that about 32% of the changes in dividend policy of the consumer goods firms in Nigeria can be explained by corporate governance. This implies that about 68% of the factor that influence dividend policy was not accounted for by corporate governance. The F-statistics is used to test the overall effect of the model. The F-statistics is 6.2100 with p.value of 0.0102 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Since the p.value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the study concludes that corporate governance accounts for about 32% of the dividend policy quoted of the consumer goods sector firms in Nigeria.

The results of the coefficient of independent variable is used to produce equation of the relationship from the model as given below:

$$DPR_{it} = 7.7126 + 3.7458BI^* + 0.3319BS - 1.6223IO^* - 3.9105CEOD^{**} + 3.2310MO - 2.6691OC - 0.4506FS$$

****significant at 5%, *significant at 1%**

From the above equation and Table 10, the model for corporate governance and dividend policy nexus revealed a positive board independence (3.7458), board size (0.3319), and managerial ownership (3.2310). This implies that BI, BS and MO increment will improve dividend pays by consumer good firms in Nigeria.

Other corporate governance variables including institutional ownership (-1.6223), Chief Executive Officer Duality (-3.9105), and Ownership concentration (-2.6691) had negative relationship with dividend policy. Again, the control variable being Firm size (-0.4506) showed negative relationships. This implies that a unit increase in the variable leads to a fall in dividend payout. This means that IO, CEOD, and OC have adverse effects on dividend payment.

The t-statistic and the corresponding p.values for the variables are: BI = 4.7499 (0.0060), BS = 0.8054 (0.4235), IO = -8.1521 (0.0096), CEOD = -2.4963 (0.0395), MO = 0.4509 (0.6536), OC = -0.5178 (0.6064), and FS = -0.5497 (0.5845). From the results, the p.values for BI, IO and CEOD are less than 0.05 level of significance, thus we reject the null hypothesis of no significant effects. However, the

variable: BS, Mo, OC and FS have p.values greater than 0.05 and thus we reject the null hypothesis and infer that they do not have significant effects.

Hypotheses Testing

The test for hypotheses adopted a three stage approach. Stage one involved the restatement of hypotheses in null and alternate form. Stage two involved the analyses of results while stage three stated the decision taken for each hypothesis. Each test was conducted at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis One

Corporate governance has no significant effect on dividend payout ratio of quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Model 1: $DPR_{it} = 7.7126 + 3.7458BI^* + 0.3319BS - 1.6223IO^* - 3.9105CEOD^{**} + 3.2310MO - 2.6691OC - 0.4506FS$

$R^2 = 36\%$ (F = 6.2100, P < 0.05)

Note: * denotes significant at 1%, ** denotes significant at 5%; *** denote significant at 10%.

The coefficient of determination is 0.36 with F-statistics with p.value less than 0.05 level of significance. Also, the coefficients of regression for BI, IO and CEOD had p.values less than 0.05 level of significance. The p.values for BS, MO and OC are greater than 0.05 level of significance. From the results, we reject the null hypothesis for the overall effect of the model, and also reject the null hypothesis for individual effects of BI, IO and CEOD. However, we cannot reject the null hypothesis of the individual coefficients, BS, MO and OC, effect on DPR. **Decision:** Corporate governance has significant effect, driven by board independence (BI), institutional ownership (IO) and Chief Executive Officer Duality (CEOD) on the dividend policy of consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Corporate characteristics are determinants of dividend policies of quoted firms in Nigeria. This study showed that corporate governance, firm profitability, firm liquidity, and firm size are drivers of dividend policies in Nigeria. Among these variables, board independence, net profit margin ratio, current ratio, total asset and market capitalisation showed significant positive effects and hence are the drivers of firm high dividend payout ratio. However, institutional ownership and Chief Executive Officer Duality had significant negative effects, and thus causes low dividend payout ratio among quoted consumer goods firm in Nigeria. These results emanated from Radom effect models which imply that these outcomes are common among the quoted firms at all times.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the recommendations is that investors in the consumer goods industry should look out for firms that encourage independent directors, Chief Executive Officer Duality and institutional ownership. This will motivate firms to discourage earnings retention and encourage higher dividend payment. The management of consumer goods firms should consider the net profit margin as yardstick for dividend policy. This means that increasing net profit margin should be seem as litmus indicator for higher dividend. Firms in the consumer goods sector should consider their capital structure before dividend policy. Management of consumer goods firms should only consider dividend payment if it considers that the firm as adequate liquidity and the study recommends that investors with risk adverse attitude needing quick return on investment should consider larger firms that have higher propensity to pay dividend.

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